

Perceived Involvement, Benefits, and Teachers Outcomes of Program Accreditation

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Abstract:- Accreditation sets standard procedures in evaluating institutions or programs to determine whether they operate at basic quality levels. The accreditation process enhances the institution's best practices in developing a quality culture and securing administrative support. This study investigated teachers' perceived involvement and benefits as outcomes of program accreditation in a private university. The study used descriptive-correlational and phenomenological approaches. There were 98 faculty selected through random sampling. The study was conducted in one of the universities in Ozamiz City, Philippines. The data were gathered through a questionnaire and analyzed using the weighted mean, standard deviation, and Pearson r Correlation Coefficient. Results showed that the respondents were highly involved, possessed a high level of self-esteem, and had enhanced self-confidence. The school administration of highly motivated teachers, as the outcome of the accreditation, also benefits from the process as it gains a "stamp of approval" for meeting the minimum standard as a Higher Educational Institution. Teacher effectiveness is likewise gained as an accreditation benefit by the students because the school becomes a good learning organization. It is recommended that the University submits for a higher level of accreditation to enhance the outcomes and benefits gained by the school administration, the teachers, and the students.

Keywords:- *Administrative Support, High Motivation, Learning Organization, Quality Education, Teacher Effectiveness,*

I. INTRODUCTION

Increasing the quality of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) is the goal of the Commission on Higher Education, which is looking for strategies for attaining quality standards among HEIs. Reforms are being set in places such as rationalizing the structure of higher education and improving the higher education budget to ensure resource mobilization and cost-effectiveness (De Boer et al., 2016). However, these reforms will not be enough if HEIs are not pressured to constantly improve and comply with set standards above the CHED minimum requirements. Yap (2012) stressed that the low quality of HEIs in the country affects the economy's growth. Moreover, with globalization and the growing demands for skilled workers, it is imperative to improve the quality of

education, and one way is through establishing a credible accreditation system.

Accreditation is one way that HEIs keep themselves in check with the standard. In the Philippines, accreditation of individual programs and institutions is voluntary. It is emphasized and mandated in CMO No. 1 s., 2005. Institutional or program accreditation merits autonomy, funding, and subsidies to institutions or program projects. Since accreditation is voluntary, only a few universities and colleges submit for accreditation. HEIs in most developed countries are undergoing accreditation of their various programs to get a strong collaboration among academe and industries and for internationalization (Chavez, Dotong, Camello, & Labrador, 2016). The accreditation process involves substantial time and financial resources (Raehsler, 2018). During the accreditation process, the faculty and staff play an important role before and during an accreditation visit.

Accreditation is only possible with collaboration. Collaboration helps group members to see the bigger picture so that a panoramic view of assessment and continuous progress is possible (Ben-Isaac, 2013). Germain & Spencer (2016) demonstrated a clear increase in collaboration among faculty preparing for accreditation review. To better manage the accreditation process, leaders must not only have a clear grasp of the task required but also employ empathy to recognize the perceptions of faculty involved in the process (Germaine & Spencer, 2016). The study by Bangert & Gratch (2019) claimed that the role of librarians in the formal accreditation review is minimal. The librarian involvement is only evident during the writing of the institutional self-study, standards regarding the library and learning resources, and during the site visit when they are assessed and interviewed by the accreditors.

Another study (Hail et al., 2019) showed that the faculty participants viewed national accreditation as a benefit in terms of enhanced status and prestige for both the university and individual programs and increased opportunities to entice a higher quality of students, faculty, and funding. However, the faculty voiced concern about the time and stressed that a national accreditation review costs faculty. Not only did they feel they had little voice in the decision to pursue national accreditation, but their participation was gross.

According to Bucalos (2014), faculty morale improves as they take a more vested interest or "ownership" in accreditation. Faculty support can be stronger if faculty know the facts and

have answers to their questions before beginning the journey. In addition, the faculty needs to be appreciated for their intensive work, such as developing quality assessments and analyzing documents. Refraining from failing or undervaluing the work required for accreditation undermines faculty willingness to participate. In the study of Hail et al. (2019), faculty confided that institutions could demonstrate appreciation by allowing faculty to do the following: 1) include accreditation work as part of their scholarship or tenure/promotion materials with appropriate credit; 2) receive varying teaching loads commensurate with their assigned accreditation work; or 3) receive incentive pay for work beyond the scope of their regular workloads.

Institutional or program accreditation is a process complied by the HEIs on the standards that certify the competency and credibility of an institution (Pavlakis & Kelley, 2016). The faculty has an enormous responsibility and is a key player before and during accreditation. However, the study by Kremer and Horton (2016) showed that the accreditation process is more of the responsibility of an administrator and less involvement among faculty. Less work delegation among faculty members or fewer awareness results in anxiety and panic among the faculty members, particularly those new to the organization (Bucalos, 2014). Lewis (2016) qualitative study identified that lack of time as the central theme.

Another study on the nursing faculty's job satisfaction during accreditation (Lee, Miller, Kippenbrock, Rosen, and Emory, 2017) disclosed that the faculty felt the extreme pressure exerted by the accreditors. These pressures are compliance in meeting program outcomes, attaining the school vision and mission, and preparations for classroom observations. They also found that the pressure on accreditation is a significant factor in the faculty's increased turnover rate (Lee et al., 2017). Bucalos (2014) reported that faculty is an outsiders during the accreditation process as they are delegated fewer tasks and fewer responsibilities. However, Greenberg (2012) claimed that faculty participation during accreditation is vital. The faculty who are more involved in the accreditation process display to accreditors that they are interested in the accreditation outcomes. This study examined the perceived involvement, benefits, and teachers' outcomes of program accreditation in a private university.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational design that involves collecting data from the population of interest to examine the preoperative leadership of operating nurse supervisors, patient safety, and recovery. The data were elicited through a modified research questionnaire. The data were treated, tallied, and statistically before they were analyzed and interpreted. The selected design allows flexibility in investigating and describing the relationship between independent and dependent variables.

The study was conducted in the different accredited colleges/programs in one of the private universities in Ozamiz City. Ozamiz City is a third-class city in Misamis Occidental, Philippines. It has 141,828 people as of 2015 (NSO 2015). Ozamiz City is close to Zamboanga del Sur, Zamboanga Sibugay, and Zamboanga del Norte provinces, while across the bay is Lanao del Norte. The presence of two universities makes Ozamiz City a premier education center in Northern Mindanao.

This non-sectarian institution of learning offered twenty-two (22) programs. The university submitted for voluntary accrediting agencies. Currently, the university has twenty-two (22) programs accredited by PACUCOA at different levels, ISA accredited, and ISO certified with the new standard-ISO 9001:2015. As a result of the accreditations, the three programs: the College of Education, College of Criminology, and College of Computer Science, were awarded as Center of Development in Region 10. In addition, the university is enjoying the benefits of an autonomous school in Northern Mindanao.

The study's respondents were ninety-eight (98) faculty members currently employed at the university, selected through purposive random sampling. The selection criteria were: 1) A faculty in one of the university's accredited programs; 2) Has been involved in the preparation of documents and participated in any school accreditation activities; and 3) Has given consent to participate. This study utilized researcher-made questionnaires, validated, pilot-tested, and yielded a Cronbach's Alpha above 0.7 and a modified instrument developed by Rosenberg (1965) for self-esteem and Jones (2001) for self-confidence.

Before conducting the research study, permission was obtained from the Office of the Graduate School for the researcher to gather data. Then, permission was secured from the Office of the Vice President for Academic Affairs and the deans of the identified colleges. When granted, the researcher personally did the actual data gathering. Other important research activities like tallying responses, data organization, analysis, and interpretation of data followed.

The research respondents were not subjected to harm in any way. On the contrary, respect for the respondents' dignity was prioritized. First, the protection of the privacy of research respondents, an adequate level of confidentiality of the research data, and the anonymity of individuals participating in the research were ensured. Second, deception and exaggeration about the aims and objectives of the research will be avoided, and affiliations in any form, sources of funding, and any possible conflicts of interest will be declared. Third, any communications about the research were done with honesty and transparency, and any misleading information and the representation of primary data findings were avoided.

Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the respondents' level of involvement in the program accreditation. The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient or Pearson's *r* was used to testing the significant relationship between the respondents' perceived involvement and benefits and teachers' outcomes of program accreditation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Respondents' Perceived Involvement in the Program Accreditation

Table 1 presents the respondents' level of involvement in program accreditation. The data in the table shows that the faculty have a high level of involvement during accreditation. An average weighted mean of 3.31 supports their claim. It implies that the faculty currently assigned in the department who have undergone PACUCOA program accreditation highly participated in preparing the documents and were actively involved in all activities about accreditation.

This study conforms to the study of Gerbic and Kranenburg (2010) demonstrated an increase in collaboration among faculty preparing for accreditation. The study of Greenfield, Pawsey, & Braithwaite (2011) revealed that faculty were motivated to participate, and the benefits that accrue to them can be positively self-enforcing. Participants desire to engage with colleagues to learn and validate their efforts to improve services. (Prados, Peterson, & Lattuca, 2005) reported that faculty members who generally supported continuous improvement were moderate to a high levels of participation in decision-making. However, there is an increase in participation in the support for curriculum development and revision.

Faculty plays an important role in the accreditation process to ensure academic integrity and self-regulation (Winterton, 2017). The faculty member's role within the university is vital to the success and progress of an institution; however, even though all these activities are pivotal, most faculty cannot engage in all of their activities (Bensimon, Dowd, Stanton-Salazar, & Dávila, 2019). Faculty time spent on instruction (Benedict & Benedict, 2014) has decreased due to the administrator's expectations and other tasks to comply with. Tenure and promotion are among the faculty's most recognizable and common rewards (Alperin et al., 2019; Vuong, Rowe, Hoyt, & Carrier, 2017; Croom, 2017).

In this study, faculty members are involved in the accreditation process. They form part of the committees that prepare the self-survey instrument, rating the different key areas of accreditation after a thorough review of how the university has met and improved the standards since the previous visit for the programs. The faculty prepared the documents and constituted the evidence supporting the rating they had given in every area. In the accreditation process, the faculty imbibe a culture of excellence as they practice Deming's cycle of Plan-Do-Check-Act, also known as the PDCA cycle (Dudin et al., 2015). It is a model for continuous quality improvement. It is a

repetitive cycle of identifying what needs to be improved for change (Plan); executing the plan (Do); checking or studying the results to see if they meet the expected outcomes (Check), and taking action to improve the process (Act). This cycle allows not only the faculty but also the school administrators or management level to review or revisit the university's vision, mission, and objectives and project things that need to do or incorporated into its medium or long-range Development Plan, thus, allowing the school for continuous improvement.

Table 1. Respondents' Perceived Involvement in the Program Accreditation

Variable	WM	Stdev	I
Perceived Involvement	3.31	0.59	High

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very High (VH) 1.26-2.25 Low
2.26-3.25 High (H) 1.00-1.25 Very Low (VL)

The accreditation process allows the teachers to work collaboratively with their co-teachers, particularly in the documentation process and in constituting the exhibits. During this process, the faculty work overtime with their co-teachers exchanging experiences in and out of the classroom. As a result, camaraderie is developed while preparing the exhibits making the teachers realize that sharing the burden or workload is still fun despite their hectic schedules and teaching preparations for the accreditation visit. In addition, the involvement process allows the teachers to immerse themselves in the university culture.

B. Respondents' Perceived Benefits in the Program Accreditation

Table 2 presents the data in determining the respondents' perceived benefits of the program accreditation. This study categorizes benefits into the students, faculty, and administration. It is perceived that students benefit the most from any program accreditation. It is supported by the obtained weighted mean of 3.62. The benefits for the faculty follow this, and the last is the benefits for the administration. Although, the continuum falls at a very high level. The findings conform to (Roberts, Johnson, & Groesbeck, 2004) that accreditation benefits the school, students, and faculty.

Prados, Peterson, & Lattuca, 2005 said that the faculty perceptions of institutional reward systems might influence individual decisions about participation in activities related to undergraduate education, such as curriculum development, instruction, or assessment. The faculty and program surveys asked about respondents' perceptions of changes over the past ten years in the emphasis on teaching in hiring, promotion, tenure, and merit salary decisions. In another study, the respondents agreed that accreditation was beneficial; they also thought there were no standardized measures to assess such perceived benefits. The result indicates a greater need to disseminate information to employers and site supervisors regarding the benefits of accreditation (Scofield & Hof, 2007).

Students' understanding of the importance of accreditation has a 60% higher impact on their academic success than their comprehension of the program's strategic goals or schools. The value of accreditation and the help of academic organizations develop an awareness of programs focused on this value. Such awareness campaigns can strengthen the efforts of organizations pursuing accreditation by providing them with the direct help of their students (Kafaji, 2020).

Gassman & Thompson (2017) addressed the major benefits of accreditation for institutions related to quality assurance, creation, and adoption of common core standards, sharing of improvement processes between institutions, improved work opportunities for students, and greater public knowledge and appreciation, leading to increased enrolment and donor support.

Table 2. Respondents' Perceived Benefits in the Program Accreditation

Construct	WM	Stdev	I
Students	3.62	0.44	Very High
Faculty	3.56	0.48	Very High
Administration	3.49	0.55	Very High
Overall Weighted Mean	3.56	0.06	Very High

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very High (VH) 1.26-2.25 Low
2.26-3.25 High (H) 1.00-1.25 Very Low (VL)

The very high result on the perceived benefits of accreditation by the students, faculty, and administration implies that the students and graduates are aware that accreditation is some status symbol and credential which signifies that the program they have enrolled in or have completed had complied with the standards mandated by regulatory bodies such as CHED and TESDA.

Accreditation serves the purpose of safeguarding the stakeholders' interests as the HEIs commit themselves to continuous improvement. Most graduates realize that being a graduate of an accredited program makes it easier to seek employment, knowing they have the advantage over the other graduates. Again, this is a stamp of prestige and approval. For faculty members, they develop a keen awareness of the possibility that they too can become evaluators, and participate in accreditation visits, be able to share ideas on the current developments in curriculum development, implementation, and monitoring, exposing them to other education specialists, allowing their mother or host institutions to keep abreast with the growth and development of other member institutions as they share best practices. It creates a sense of pride among the faculty.

C. Respondents' Perceived Teachers' Outcomes of Program Accreditation

Table 3 presents the data in determining the respondents' perceived teachers' accreditation outcomes. Perceived results are listed as faculty self-esteem and faculty self-confidence. The data shows that the faculty has high self-esteem and self-confidence. A faculty with positive self-esteem and high self-confidence engages more in students learning outcomes than those with negative self-esteem and lack self-confidence.

Teachers during accreditation felt they had the opportunity to show their teaching skills to the accreditors. Having what they saw as "lessons that went well" reflects what Bandura (1986) called mastery experiences (Idris, 2017).

The teachers shared that their confidence was enhanced because of their teaching environment. Another study showed that teachers believed national accreditation was important for enhanced status and prestige. The faculty also noted that their workload was a drawback unless faculty were recognized for their work (Hail, Hurst, Chang, & Cooper, 2019). Accreditation is a force for accountability, but it also leverages new opportunities and stimulates innovative and transformative educational environments that shape the preparation of teachers (Kaufman, 2018). Accredited institution or program complies with the standard that signifies competency and credibility in the programs offered.

Table 3. Respondents' Perceived Teachers' Outcomes of Program Accreditation

Construct	WM	Stdev	I
Self -Esteem	2.78	0.41	High
Self-Confidence	3.08	0.32	High
Overall Weighted Mean	2.93	0.21	High

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very High (VH) 1.26-2.25 Low
2.26-3.25 High (H) 1.00-1.25 Very Low (VL)

D. Significant Relationship between Respondents' Perceived Involvement and Teachers' Outcomes of Program Accreditation

Table 4 shows the data to determine the significant relationship between faculty-perceived involvement and outcomes of program accreditation. The teachers' outcome is categorized into self-esteem and self-confidence. The result revealed that teachers' outcomes as to self-esteem were not significantly affected by their involvement in the accreditation. The obtained r value is 0.075, with a p-value of 0.465. On the other hand, the teachers' level of involvement in the accreditation process significantly influences their self-confidence. The R-value of 0.305 with a p-value of 0.00* confirmed the significant positive relationship. It implies that involvement in the accreditation enhances the teachers' self-confidence.

A study on teacher attitudes and accreditation outcomes showed a significant increase in scores among teachers in schools without accreditation. A teacher with a positive attitude about the process of their answer corresponds with the actual practice in the school (Ulmer, 2015). Another study by Mullen revealed that the teachers are overwhelmed with the accreditation process due to the enormous paper works to be completed, resulting in what they felt was "busy work" that took time away that could have been used to better prepare for the visit mainly for the classroom observation (Mullen, 2001). Another study by Mullen showed that while the teachers

expressed pleasure in building their school improvement plan, they were dismayed by the requirements to write action plans using a specific format with specific vocabulary.

Another study on the teachers' perception of the accreditation process found that the accreditation process had a positive effect on school change and student success. However, they also found that even though the participants felt it was a worthwhile process, they indicated that they often needed more adequate resources for working on accreditation (Wood, 1999).

Table 4. Significant Relationship between Respondents' Perceived Involvements and Teachers' Outcomes of Program Accreditation

Variables	Test of Significance		Remarks
	r value	p-value	
Perceived Involvement and Teachers' Outcomes as to: Self -Esteem Self-Confidence	0.075 0.305	0.465 0.00**	Not Significant Highly Significant

*Legend: 0.00-0.01** Highly Significant 0.02-0.05* Significant above 0.05 Not Significant*

Accreditation ensures that every student in an accredited school receives a quality education. The experiences the teachers encountered in the process of accreditation enhanced their self-confidence. The teachers' positive attitude radiated confidence in students, making them develop a positive attitude towards learning. Teachers' attitudes and beliefs play a very significant role in shaping classroom practices (Bolhuis & Voeten, 2004). Like any attitude, a teacher's positive attitude can be measured by their emotional response. In this study, the emotional respondent is the teachers' self-esteem and self-confidence. Asiyai (2016) finding showed that effective teachers produced better student performance.

The faculty should be motivated to become involved in the accreditation process because it provides an opportunity for them to be involved in institutional self-improvement activities (Allstate, 2004) hence increasing their self-self-confidence for being a part of the school's improvement.

E. Significant Relationship between Respondents' Perceived Benefits and Teachers' Outcomes of Program Accreditation

Table 5 presents the data in determining the relationship between perceived teachers' benefits (students, faculty, and administration) and outcome program accreditation (self-

esteem, self-confidence). The data showed that self-esteem does not influence teachers' outcomes in the entire construct. The p-value is above 0.05, implying an insignificant relationship between the independent and dependent variables. On the other hand, the construct of self-confidence was affected by the benefits of program accreditation. The p-value of the entire construct is lower than 0.05, resulting in a significant relationship among the variables. The finding implies that teachers' self-confidence increases due to the benefits of the accreditation for themselves, the students, and the administration.

Although faculty spend much time working on accreditation tasks assigned to them, they recognize the value of accreditation in improving education delivery and providing students with a quality education. The study by (Connely & McMahon, 2007) found that teachers could articulate how they benefited professionally and how learning and teaching in their classrooms in the accreditation process. International accreditation can help institutions to implement world-class practices in teaching, learning, and administration, enhance faculty and staff morale, and increases graduates' employability and acceptance in the global education and job market (Memon & Gangoor, 2017).

Table 5. Significant Relationship between Respondents' Perceived Benefits and Teachers' Outcomes of Program Accreditation

Variables	Test of Significance		Remarks
	<i>r value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
Perceived Benefits and Teachers' Outcomes as to:			
Students			
Self -Esteem	0.026	0.026	Not Significant
Self-Confidence	0.219	0.03*	Significant
Faculty			
Self -Esteem	0.125	0.219	Not Significant
Self-Confidence	0.344	0.00**	Highly Significant
Administration			
Self -Esteem	0.040	0.692	Not Significant
Self-Confidence	0.218	0.031*	Significant

Legend: 0.00-0.01** Highly Significant 0.02-0.05* Significant above 0.05 Not Significant

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The teachers are highly involved in their program accreditation for the various benefits for the students, faculty, and administration. The teachers possessed a high level of self-esteem and self-confidence. The teachers' participation in the accreditation process enhances their self-confidence. The administration may encourage faculty and staff to participate in accreditation. A policy on the reward and benefits is incorporated in the faculty handbook for the faculty to be motivated and actively participate during accreditation. Further study is to be conducted on the faculty perceptions of the school accreditation and the effects of accreditation in improving the delivery of quality education based on enrollment and graduates' employability.

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